

Brain Freeze: the Importance of Culture and Language in Shaping Rich Semantic Thoughts

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Abstract

In recent years, the use of brain implants has revolutionized the way people can share and communicate their thoughts and feelings. In this paper, we investigate how the relationship between culture and language can impact the perception of snow, by capturing and semantic processing the brain waves of five individuals. The participants, originally natives from different parts of the world, were exposed to different types of snow in a Winter Dome. The participants' brain waves were measured and recorded, allowing for a detailed analysis of the neural activity of their semantic thoughts. Moreover, the participants were asked to annotate their perceptions of snow and semantic thoughts using the Universal Thought Ontology from WikiMind. The results of this study suggest that culture and language play a significant role in shaping the way individuals perceive different types of snow. Specifically, the study found that individuals from regions with a greater abundance of snow tended to have more complex and nuanced semantic associations with different types of snow. The findings of this study contribute to our greater understanding of how culture and language shape cognitive processes, and offer insights into the neural mechanisms underlying the semantic processing of verbal and non-verbal cues.

Keywords

Semantic Thoughts, Brain Waves, Solid thought^s, Snow

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1. Introduction

Through the use of brain implants, individuals can share their thoughts and emotions with others in a way that transcends language barriers. This has revolutionized communication and has led to a deeper understanding and appreciation of the diversity of human experience. The computational models used in conjunction with these brain implants provide a comprehensive understanding of the human psyche. By analyzing patterns in thoughts and emotions, these models can identify commonalities and differences between individuals and cultures. This has led to new insights in fields such as psychology, sociology, and anthropology.

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Overall, the use of ontology alignment for brain implants has led to a more connected and empathetic world. The ability to share thoughts and emotions has brought people closer together, and the computational models used have provided a deeper understanding of the human psyche. This work represents a significant step forward in the field of semantic web technologies and has the potential to transform the way we understand and interact with each other.

The meaning of words is often not explicit - one word can be meant by the sender in one way, and perceived by the receiver in an opposite one. The changes in the meaning of words can be dependant on a variety of individual aspects, such as social background and voice tone. This is made even worse by the fact that the meaning of words is constantly changing. Therefore, in order to enhance communication and avoid misconceptions and misunderstanding we think that the real meaning of words has to be made explicit. In this research we propose a method to analysis different meanings of words, using brain waves technology.

2. Related Research

In this section, we describe the main building blocks used to base our experiment on. First in a broad overview of the history of brain implants, followed by a summary of the current state of the art of Semantic thought models.

2.1. Brain Wave Reading

The first major breakthrough in brain wave research came from the research team of Letters [1], who created the system BetaThink, which was created to participate in the popular TV program “Are you thinking what I’m thinking?”. The program consisted of two participants connected to two brain wavers, with the goal for each participant being to change the output of the brain waver of the other participant to a pre-defined output shape. The idea was that the participants needed to change the other person’s mind without getting distracted by each other.

Initial reactions to the participation of BetaThink were skeptical, claiming the brain wave monitor of BetaThink displayed a simple video since it could not be possible to display a machine “thinking”. This led to the groundbreaking publication [2] from the same Letters team, by highly increasing the fidelity of the brain wavers they proved that not only were the brain scans of BetaThink influenceable by outside stimuli, but they were also consistent with the same high fidelity version brain waves of a human test group.

The discovery of distinct, discrete and readable, brain waves lead to a renewed focus on brain wave reading technology, replacing the cumbersome brain waves scanners with barely intrusive brain implants [3]. Due to the low cost of the brain implants the adaptation proved to be high, as were the possible applications [4].

However, the initial security of the implants proved to be lacking, allowing, for example, highly specified advertisements, reacting directly to what people were thinking while browsing online [5]. The solution came in the shape of a refurbished idea from the past, the solid thought^s, a protected environment where only you decide who and what has access to your semantic thoughts [6].

2.2. Semantic Thoughts

With the solid thought^s also came the final standardized representation for brain waves, *semantic thoughts*, a unified model of thought concepts [7]. The semantic thoughts model was built on proven semantic web concepts, by connecting each individual thought as a unique concept, labeled with the concept that the thought represents. The labels are always added personally since this happens within the solid thought^s.

Due to the personal labeling of the semantic thoughts, cultural differences have an impact on which semantic thoughts are labeled [8]. For example, Dutch people can make more distinctions between different waterways, and Inuit people can make more distinctions between different kinds of snow. Interestingly the semantic thoughts are not only available for the Dutch or Inuit people, but the semantic thought patterns are also available for labeling for people from other cultures, but they are not recognized as being distinctly different from already labeled concepts and are therefore left alone.

With the revolutionary discovery of semantic thought technologies came the problem of visualising these thoughts. A breakthrough in cognitive science came in the form of *cognigrams*, a circular, visual representation of the semantic thoughts [9]. And a half a decade later, the First International Cognigram Dictionary [10] has been created, which has since been serving as a standard tool for analysing and interpreting cognigrams.

In this research we make a first step into filling in these blanks, by aligning the spectrum of semantic thoughts of different cultures, therefore contributing to a deeper understanding of the universality of the human experience.

3. Methods

3.1. Experimental Design

The experiment took place inside a Winter Dome, a controlled environment where seasonality, temperature, and natural conditions can be simulated in a controlled manner. The participants stayed inside the Winter Dome, during which different types of snow were presented to them. The five types of snow included powder snow, crud, slush snow, frozen snow, and corn snow. Participants were instructed to turn their implants to open-source mode to allow the researchers to record their activity and were asked to describe each of the five types of snow presented to them. Each type of snow was presented for 30 seconds, and participants were asked to provide a verbal description during this time. There was a 30-second break between each type of snow to allow participants to relax and prepare for the next trial. The order of presentation was randomized across participants to control for order effects. Once the data was collected, a virtual agent annotated the brain waves data using the Universal Thought Ontology (UTO) [11] from WikiMind [12]. The annotation was made by a virtual agent in order to minimize biases, as the agent does not require the use of a specific language to annotate the concepts and their relative brain wave data.

3.2. Participants Selection and Data Collection

The study included five participants, four natives of European countries and one indigenous person of the Arctic. More specifically, a Dutch person (id:1 - Roderick), a Hungarian person (id:2 - Mark), an Italian person (id:3 - Margherita), an English person (id:4 - John), and an Inuk person (id:5 - Ikumak). The selection of participants from different countries was intentionally aimed to target how concepts are perceived by different cultures. We expected that the European participants are more likely to have similar notions and perceptions of the same concept, compared to the Inuk person.

3.3. Analysis and Evaluation

At the end of the experiment, the full corpus of annotated data has been merged and harmonized by the virtual agent. The data analysis aimed at finding different ways each stage of snow was conceptualized by each participant.

4. Results

The annotations of the recorded semantic thoughts show that the Inuk participant has the most linguistically precise conceptions of the different types of snow, while the other participants needed to borrow more general adjectives to describe the same texture or consistency (see Table 1).

Figure 1: The cognigram representation of each participant's semantic thoughts associated with the general word 'snow'. The cognigram suggests that the Inuk person has the richest notion of the concept. For a complete analysis of the cognigrams, please refer to [10].

The semantic thoughts associated with the annotation suggest that individuals that are more exposed to snow have a significantly larger body of memories and experiences that affect the formation of thoughts when encountering the different forms of snow. These results are well reflected in the cognigram as shown in Figure 1. There is a striking similarity of the Dutch and Hungarian participants perception and conception of snow, which might be explained by the geographical and topographical similarity of the countries, and the participant's similarity of experiences. The Italian person has had most of the experiences related to snow from sports activities such as skiing. However a complete analysis of the cognigrams is outside of the scope of this pilot study and left for future work.

Table 1

Vocabulary for different types of snow in different languages.

Description	English	Dutch	Hungarian	Italian	Inuk
powdered snow	powdersnow	poedersneeuw	porhó	nevischio	tlapa
coarse snow	snow	sneeuw	hó	neve	pukak
melted snow	snow	smurrie	latyakos hó	aquaneve	qanik
frozen snow	snow	sneeuw	hó	neve	nilak
corn snow	snow	sneeuw	hó	neve	qinu

5. Discussion and Future Work

Culture is a complex and multifaceted phenomena, and it can have a significant impact on the way people perceive and understand various concepts. Different cultures often have different notions and variations of a concept, and this can be reflected in their vocabulary. In this research we showed that sharing the semantic thoughts of a person from a culture that has a more nuanced perception of a concept can lead to a better understanding of the concept from people of different cultures.

The present study represents an important contribution to the Semantic Web and Semantic Thoughts fields, by shedding light on the neural mechanisms underlying the processing of semantic concepts. However, there is still much to be explored and investigated in this area. One avenue for future research would be to expand the scope of the study to include a larger and more diverse sample of participants from different cultures and backgrounds. This would allow for a more comprehensive understanding of how brain waves vary across individuals and populations, and how culture and language impact the neural processing of semantic concepts. Additionally, future research could investigate the temporal dynamics of brain activity during semantic processing. By using advanced neuroimaging techniques such as EEG and MEG, it may be possible to investigate the precise timing of brain activity associated with semantic processing, and how this varies across different individuals and cultures. Another promising direction for future work would be to investigate the role of individual differences in brain structure and function in semantic processing. By examining individual differences in brain connectivity, grey matter volume, and other structural and functional properties, it may be possible to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the neural mechanisms underlying semantic processing. Finally, future research could investigate the potential applications of these findings in clinical and therapeutic contexts. For example, it may be possible to use these findings to develop new interventions and therapies for individuals with language and semantic processing disorders, such as aphasia or semantic dementia. For example, it would be possible to run approximation algorithms to find the nearest semantic concepts to someone's thoughts.

In conclusion, while the present study represents an important contribution to the Semantic Web, there is still much to be learned and discovered about the neural mechanisms underlying semantic processing. Future research in this area holds great promise for advancing our understanding of how the brain processes thoughts and expand our knowledge of Semantic Thoughts.

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